

COMPOSITE SINE WAVE BEAM DEVELOPMENT

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Sine wave shear webs have been efficient aircraft structures that are difficult to fabricate in metal. In composites, these manufacturing limitations do not apply, allowing designers to take advantage of the full efficiency of sine wave shear webs.

However, early industry attempts at fabricating composite sine wave parts experienced problems in the tight corner between the web and the cap strips. These problems showed up in the form of fiber bunching, fiber distortion and voids. Boeing has solved these problems through development of a unique configuration that produces a smooth blending of fibers in the transition from the web to chord.

The solution features a web to cap two stage transition of 45° each. This transition is made without stretching, distorting or cutting the fabric resulting in a smooth transition. The result is a triangular shaped cavity in the cap which is filled with 0° fibers to produce a bundle of highly efficient material which is continuous for the length of the cap.

This configuration is easily modified to tailor the amount of uniaxial material in the chord bundle to match the load in the beam caps. This is done by adding material to the bundle to produce alternate shapes. Variation in the height of the chord bundle produces changes in the area of the cap without changing the sine wave configuration. Boeing has demonstrated the producibility of these configurations.

Incorporation of a "house" shaped unidirectional bundle produces an added benefit in the case where there is a high normal load on the unidirectional cap material within the beam structure. The amplitude of the sine wave is designed to match the width of the bundle and provides a direct load path between the upper and lower caps through bondline shear transfer at the cap and tension/compression in the web.

The result of these developments is an efficient sine wave beam which has the capability to carry high loads in its caps. Possible applications in aircraft structures are in spars, load redistribution ribs, and body frames.

A unique application for this concept was found in the preliminary design of a blended wing/fuselage supercruiser composite fighter. In this airplane the fuselage frames extend out into the wing to carry the wing bending loads.

These loads must be carried in the frame caps through the wing/fuselage blended area and around the fuselage.

The sine wave frame design that satisfied these requirements will be shown. The cap end loads are carried in 0° bundles of GR/EP that are tailored to match the load and are continuous from tip to tip. The sine wave web provides the radial support to the caps in the fuselage and their vertical support in the wing. In the wing/fuselage blended area the radial loads become large which requires support on both sides from sandwich webs. The sandwich also allows a transition from the vertical position in the wing to the radial position in the fuselage. A quarter size frame segment was fabricated to demonstrate its producibility.